

BUILDING A WDME-CENTRIC SYNTHETIC DATA INFRASTRUCTURE FOR THE WATERVERSE PROJECT

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ABSTRACT

Hydroinformatics and the on-going digitisation of the water industry provides unparalleled opportunities in the collecting, processing, and analysis of water-related data, leading to information and knowledge. However, the abundance of vast amounts of data makes it easy for water sector operatives to get lost in a sea of data. The WATERVERSE project [1] seeks to address this through the research and development of a water data management ecosystem (WDME), a modular platform that enables the collection, harmonisation, processing, and visualisation of a wide range of water source data, Figure 1.

A significant challenge for those developing modules for the WDME is the availability of suitable test data, as green field data management systems such as the WDME will typically start with a zero dataset and rely on data collected during the project to test system operations and functionality. This naturally creates the need for synthetic data to provide data for three general use-cases: data that demonstrates the end-to-end operation of the WDME, data to stress-test operations, and edge case data to demonstrate module functionality, e.g. missing data, out of range data, leaks, floods and so on.

INTRODUCTION

The WATERVERSE project [1] is an EU-funded project aimed at developing a Water Data Management Ecosystem (WDME) for making data management practices and resources in the water sector accessible, affordable, secure, fair, and easy to use, and engaged with six European water companies to embed the WDME with their processes. The WDME seeks to ingest and harmonise data from a variety of sources allowing it to be viewed and processed with the WDME's component-based architecture, Figure 1, the philosophies being that re-usable components can be deployed across a number of pilots and the visual plug-and-play approach of the WDME's mash-up editor empowers non-technical users to define and process dataflows and associated transformations, Figure 2.

Of course, a system is nothing without the data that drives it and for the WDME this was a potential issue given that the system and its processing components needed to be developed to process data but also needed data in place for initial unit and system testing. This is a common issue in projects of this nature, [2], with synthetic data often being developed in order to: 1) prove data pipelines, 2)

stress-test data pipelines to ensure sufficient computational resources for storing and processing data, and 3) provide edge-case data for testing algorithms, such as leak detection, data validation, and duplicate data removal.

Therefore, the goal of the synthetic data infrastructure component of the WDME was to provide a configurable data provision that could be applied to a set of pilots to produce data that could be used to help develop, test, and validate component functionality.

Figure 1 - WDME logical architecture

Figure 2 - Mash-up editor in WDME

METHOD

The WDME is realised as a set of inter-connected software components that communicate through the RESTful api. The synthetic data generator component is realised as a Django server with a small api allowing synthetic datasets to be created and generate data on demand and deployed as a Docker container.

The key api methods are:

```
POST add_sensor_to_pilot/pilot = <pilot_name> & sensor = <sensor_name>
```

This defines a sensor bundle for a given pilot with the sensor definition as a json body.

GET `get_data?pilot=<pilot_name> & sensor=<sensor_name> & steps = <number_of_steps>`

This returns a set of simulation results for the sensor within the pilot. Unlike other simulation models where data is calculated as time series and clients pick up the results, this data generator generates data on-demand.

POST `reset_pilot_time?pilot= <pilot_name> & time=<time_stamp>`

This allows the simulation time to be set to a given time stamp. This results in a development flow where users can configure a sensor, create a time series of data, test components using that data and then reset the time stamp to re-run test data with configurational changes.

Given the iteration time associated with authoring synthetic data processing in Python and building and deploying Docker images, only core processing functionality is Python-based, with the data management side of the generator being JSON-based, allowing data generation behaviours to be modified live with near-zero overhead.

Synthetic Chlorine prediction

PWN, a Dutch water company, wanted to generate plausible chlorine levels based on generated river flows for the Rhine River between Olst and Lobith. We were provided with historic sensor data showing historic relationships, Figure 3, that were broadly inverse.

Figure 3 - Historic flows at Olst and associated chlorine levels at Lobith.

A regression model was constructed that mapped flow to chlorine level which was used to form the base of the synthetic model. Flow was exposed as low, medium and high ranges, with flow results mapped to appropriate chlorine levels.

The synthetic model featured two parameters, Figure 4, qOlst was set by users to be low, med or high and would produce values with the ranges given. The delta limit was added to smooth the results ranges such that a reading couldn't instantly spike if the state went from, say low to high, or between values at the lower and upper limits of a given range. The cLobith parameter used the result from qOlst as a look-up into the step table.

<pre> {"name": "q0lst", "range": [{"name": "low", "range": [100,333]}, {"name": "med", "range": [334,666]}, {"name": "high", "range": [667,999]}], "type": "lookup", "delta_limit": 0.1, "output-name": "OLST" }, </pre>	<pre> {"name": "clLobith", "steps": [[50 , 136.0], [150 , 132.0], [250 , 111.0], [350 , 95.0], [450 , 89.0], [550 , 74.0], [650 , 66.0], [750 , 61.0], [850 , 47.0], [950 , 35.0], [1000 , 42.0]], "input": "q0lst", "type": "calculation", "output-name": "Lobith" } </pre>
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Figure 4 – Synthetic chlorine prediction parameters, Olst (left) and Lobith (right)

Synthetic Smart water metering

The Cyprus-based partner was looking to collect and process water consumption and leak data from a pilot of smart water meters. Using synthetic data allowed us to define a ‘virtual pilot’ of meters with differing consumption patterns and client-side leakage. The synthetic meters were programmed to report consumption hourly and could be configured to change consumption patterns and leakage on demand.

<pre> {"name": "METER-1", "range": "meter-lookup", "type": "24hr-by3-lookup", "output-name": "urn:ngsi-ld:SmartMeter:METER-1" }, {"name": "METER-1-CONTFLOW", "input": "METER-1", "type": "state_lookup", "lookup": "meter-flow-lookup", "output-name": "urn:ngsi-ld:SmartMeter:METER-1-FLOW" }, </pre>	<pre> "meter-lookup": [{"name": "normal", "range": [0,0,20,0,0,0,20,0]}, {"name": "special", "range": [1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8]}, {"name": "high", "range": [0,0,15,0,0,0,15,0]}, {"name": "high-leak", "range": [1,1,30,1,1,1,30,1]}], "meter-flow-lookup": [{"name": "normal", "value": 0}, {"name": "special", "value": 0}, {"name": "high", "value": 0}, {"name": "high-leak", "value": 1}] </pre>
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Figure 5 - Meter configuration, flow and continuous flow attributes (left) and consumption settings (right)

Each meter was defined, Figure 5, as flow and continuous flow parameters with flow calculated from a 24hr cycle of 8 by 3 hourly amounts, with hour of day being used as a lookup, and continuous flow calculated from the presence of ‘leak’ in the meter state.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Synthetic Chlorine prediction

The synthetic chlorine prediction model was the first synthetic data model created for the project and presented the challenge of moving away from our initial, but naive, model of 'dumb' data generation, where an input directly drives an output, to a more complex 'dogleg' model where an Olst value was generated from an input and then used to drive the creation of the Lobith value, essentially creating two outputs for a single external input.

This challenge was addressed through ordering the operation of data generation and allowing each value processing step to use the output from other steps, and through the collation of outputs into an array (of time steps) containing dictionaries of synthesized parameters and associated step values, Figure 6.

```
[
  {
    "urn:ngsi-ld:DeviceMeasurement:NL-RWS-2-LMW_AFVOER-Olst-OLST": 506.86,
    "urn:ngsi-ld:DeviceMeasurement:NL-RWS-2-LMW_ZOUT-Lobith-LOBH": 80.53,
    "dateObserved": "2025-06-24T00:00:00Z"
  },
  {
    "urn:ngsi-ld:DeviceMeasurement:NL-RWS-2-LMW_AFVOER-Olst-OLST": 509.46,
    "urn:ngsi-ld:DeviceMeasurement:NL-RWS-2-LMW_ZOUT-Lobith-LOBH": 79.06,
    "dateObserved": "2025-06-25T00:00:00Z"
  },
  {
    "urn:ngsi-ld:DeviceMeasurement:NL-RWS-2-LMW_AFVOER-Olst-OLST": 486.81,
    "urn:ngsi-ld:DeviceMeasurement:NL-RWS-2-LMW_ZOUT-Lobith-LOBH": 82.22,
    "dateObserved": "2025-06-26T00:00:00Z"
  }
]
```

Figure 6 - Synthetic river flow and associated chlorine levels

This model was used in the first iteration of pilots and primarily to demonstrate synthetic data generation as a 'proof-of-concept', but moreover to 'provide data pipelines', insofar as the output from the generator could be fed through the rest of the WDME at a time when the collection of actual data was still work in progress.

Synthetic Smart water metering

The synthetic smart water metering model was a late addition to the project and came from challenges in collecting live smart metering data. Much of the philosophy for the model, and associated narratives, came from the Fiware4Water project [3], where we worked on a smart metering project to 'add value' to digital water through consumption analysis and client-side leak detection.

The synthetic model in this case was initially simpler than the synthetic chlorine prediction model with just an input (meter state) leading to an output (consumption). However, the addition of continuous flow detection led to a similar 'dogleg' approach with meter state being used to drive both consumption and continuous flow parameters. The modal consumption settings, Figure 5, can be used to create 'scenario narratives' to demonstrate consumption and leakage patterns for WDME users.

CONCLUSIONS

To date, synthetic data generation has proved invaluable on the WATERVERSE project as a mechanism for injecting test data into the system without the need to brute force into the system, e.g. manually inject data into a system database. By following the WDME system architecture and developing a WDME component, we have been able to use the synthetic data generation module as a tool for both testing the fundamental operation of the WDME through ‘proof of data pipelines’ but also providing testing for edge cases with limitless instances of extreme data. We have also been able to stress-test the WDME data pipeline through the creation of bulk synthetic data (though this has normally been in error due to fat fingered typing, rather than explicit performance analysis).

From a development perspective, we found taking a piecemeal approach to development, rather than trying to define the entire synthetic data generation system at the beginning of the project afforded us a great deal of agility, which was particularly helpful in developing and re-developing functionality as project partners become more involved with data generation as the project developed.

Implementing data generation as split functionality between a python backend and JSON configuration files allowed us to define overall functionality (in python) and dynamically configure the finer points of data generation and operation interactively at run-time / test-time. While python doesn’t have huge build times associated with it, the data generation application is running in a Docker container, giving a noticeable edit-build-deploy timeline.

Moreover, the pilot configurations have allowed us and pilot users to start thinking about their pilot demonstrations as user-focused scenarios and narratives rather than just the demonstration of data moving from point A to point B and associated processing.

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